

EDUKIT AS A MULTILITERACY-BASED LEARNING MEDIA TO ENHANCE STUDENTS MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES

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Abstract

This research is the result of a long-term collaboration between Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia (UPI) and Institut Pendidikan Guru Kampus Ilmu Khas (IPGKIK Kuala Lumpur), the Kolej Islam Teknologi Antar Bangsa (KITAB, Penang), Elementary Schools, and Special Schools in Bandung, Indonesia. This research aimed to create inclusive basic literacy learning material in bags that instructors and students in early school, elementary schools, and special schools could utilize. Character, productive pedagogy, multiliteracy, HOTS (High-Level Thinking Skills), and TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) are the foundations of this media. The inquiry yielded versatile boards packaged and gathered in an "Edukit Bag" that was beautifully wrapped to make it more entertaining and convenient for instructors and students to carry. The Edukit includes nine fundamental literacy media: language and literary literacy, numeracy, science and the environment, creative literacy (craft literacy), financial literacy, cultural and citizenship literacy, culinary literacy, and family literacy. Literacy media includes giant books, micro books, pop-up books, busy books, single pictures, series of images, comics, letter cards, words, and poems. Edukit is simple to use and well-liked by teachers and kids since it is universal and can be used collaboratively by instructors, students, and parents to share knowledge and skills.

Keywords: Edukit, Multiliteracy, Multiple Intelequences

1. INTRODUCTION

Edukit is designed as a basic literacy learning medium for early childhood children, special schools, and inclusion schools (low schools that have children with disabilities/special needs). This study was motivated by changes in learning dynamics during the Covid-19 pandemic which focused more on digital media. Apart from that, teachers do not yet understand about literacy-based media, especially craft (handmade) literacy which can increase financial literacy (financial literacy) for teachers and students, both during the pandemic (outbreak) and after the pandemic. Apart from that, by making Edukit students are directed to do creative work to prevent undirected activities (disorientation) such as playing: the internet, cellphones and games

continuously. Craft literacy learning can be developed as project-based learning (Project-based Learning) and done in collaboration between teachers and students and even with parents. The results of the project can be sold in an exhibition simulation event (Market Day Exhibition) or displayed in the creative literacy corner at school.

2. EDUKIT

Tas (Bag) Edukit is the result of literacraft made by a team of researchers and children with the guidance of teachers during the pandemic. The bag is made of cardboard, cardboard, glue, duplex, gift paper, photos and colourful pictures. The superiority of Edukit as a creative & innovative learning media in inclusive schools, easy to carry and pleasant for kindergarten children, special schools, primary schools, and teachers because teaching materials are stored in "Edukit" bags. The research results are in the form of multipurpose boards that are packaged and assembled in the "Edukit Bag" to make it more pleasant and easy for teachers and students to carry. The content of Edukit consists of 9 basic literacy media: language & literary literacy, numeracy, science, digital, financial, family, craft/literacraft, citizenship and culture) in the form of: big book, mini book, pop-up book, busy book, compic (computerized pictograph), photos, picture books, letter cards, syllable cards, word cards, sentences and science/environmental texts (Hartati, 2021). This media can be used in the family environment, playgroups, and educational ecosystems to improve higher level thinking skills (KBTT/HOTS) from preschool up to the same level as elementary school.

Edu KIT Picture

Picture1- Edukit

3. METHODOLOGY

This research uses Research and Development (R & D) research methods. Research and Development (R & D) methods in the world of education are used as an innovative effort to develop products that are contextual to learning needs. The research steps taken refer to the cycle of the research method itself through the stages: (a) Study of the relevant research results related to the validity of the aspects of the product to be developed, (b) Development of the design into a product, (c) Testing of developed products and, (d) Product correction based on test results (Borg & Gall 1983).

4. RELEVANT RESEARCH STUDIES

A study of relevant research by gathering the potential of craft literacy:

4.1. Collecting Potential Craftliteracy

The implementation of this program is carried out by (a) analyzing innovation products from researcher research, both in the form of KIT and books, then looking for other craftliteracies, discussing craftliteracy,

classifying craft literacy. (b) Looking for craft literacy from the internet, books, magazines, newspapers, and from other sources. Discussing craft literacy is done to see the potential of craft literacy done by students in school, for example: from materials, estimates, tools, and so on. Classifying craft literacy is done to make it easier for trainers and teachers to apply craft literacy in the classroom with students. It is possible that there is a group of craft literacy that students can do on their own without the help of teachers and there is also craft literacy that should be modeled or involve the guidance of teachers and parents, especially for children with disabilities.

Examples of craft literacy are for example the development of the potential of culinary processing, handicrafts, learning media (big book, mini book, pop-up book, busy book, compic [computerized pictograph], photo, picture book) digital craft making from mobile phones (such as pictures, text, animation, song, video). Maybe the students have ideas to develop craft literacy according to their interests. The students can also use the potential of materials that are easily found around them.

4. 2. Preparing Trainees from Graduate Students

Craft literacy trainers for teachers, principals and parents of students are recruited from postgraduate students. The research team prepared a complete guidebook, module and learning KIT (already done) to train postgraduate students to introduce the craft literacy training program. The role of the business world and the world of industry (DUDI) is to prepare printed materials, duplicate, publish training KITS and equipment for other activities. Students will be involved in data collection, event management, literacy craft making, training, data analysis, and reporting.

4.3. Organizing a Craft Literacy Workshop for Teachers

Workshops are held in four districts and cities, namely Bandung City, West Bandung District, Sumedang District, and Pangandaran District. Teacher trainees are postgraduate students. The role of the business world and the world of industry (DUDI) is to prepare the printed package. Postgraduate students are involved in organizing workshop events, data collection, analysis, and reporting.

4.4. Organizing a Craft Literacy Workshop for Parents and Students

After conducting a workshop for teachers, a workshop was also conducted for students' parents and students. DUDI's role is to prepare printed materials. Students are involved in event management, data collection, analysis, and reporting.

4.5. Organizing National Seminars & International Seminars

National seminars are held to disseminate research at the national level. At this national seminar, findings related to craft literacy learning were discussed with researchers and seminar participants. DUDI's role is to prepare the printed file. Postgraduate students are involved in organizing events and compiling articles. International seminars are held to disseminate research at the international level, especially in the ASEAN Region. At this international seminar, lecturers exchange ideas with researchers in the global world, especially related to craft literacy findings. DUDI's role is to prepare the printed file. Postgraduate students are involved in organizing seminar events, reporting, compiling articles and proceedings.

4.6. Internal-External Monev, Reporting & RTL (Follow-Up Plan)

Monitoring and evaluation is done internally by the Chief Researcher and Head of UPI's Directorate of Innovation & Center of Excellence. External monev from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology

5. PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

Create an Edukit that contains nine basic literacies, namely: Media Literacy Language and Literature, Media Literacy Numeracy, Media Literacy Science / Environment, Media Literacy Digital, Media Literacy Financial, Media Literacy Culture, and Citizenship, Media Literacy Craft (Literacraft), Media Literacy Family (Lifelong Literacy).

5.1. Product Testing

Product testing is limited to teachers, students, and parents in primary schools and special schools in the City of Bandung and Pangandaran Regency.

5.2. Sample Study

This study uses a purposive sampling method involving a total of nine teachers consisting of primary school teachers, special schools and kindergarten teachers from three areas namely: Bandung City, Sumedang City, and Pangandaran Regency. The three areas have great potential in the field of craft literacy and tourist areas in West Java Province.

5.3. Findings

The purpose of this research is to produce learning media that can be used by teachers and students of Kindergartens, Primary Schools, and children with disabilities (deaf-mute children and slow-learning children). Media has been created during the Covid-19 pandemic in the form of a bag containing: big book, mini book, pop up book, busy book, comic, compic, pictures, letter cards, words and sentences. Examples of such media and their users are as follows:

ACTIVITIES			
Teaching Material	Writing	Content of Edukit	Craft Literacy
Arranging the Alphabet	Observing	Culture and Citizenship Literacy	Language Literacy
Matching	Playing	Science Literacy	Digital Literacy
Learning about time	Drawing	Family Literacy	Ayo Menyimak

Picture 2
Activities and Content of Edukit

6. DISCUSSION

Edukit, which was created during the Covid-19 pandemic, was very liked by teachers and students of kindergartens, primary schools, special schools and inclusive primary schools in the city of Bandung. Because the school was closed during the pandemic, only tests were conducted on primary school students and special schools (exceptional schools) in the city of Bandung. Thus, extensive testing is still needed in some schools, namely in kindergartens, inclusive primary schools and madrasahs.

Based on a limited survey, it turns out that primary school teachers like and are able to create craft literacy. According to the complete survey as follows: 1) teachers strongly agree and are able to create learning media based on verb literacy (4.5%), 2) Teachers agree (11%), 3) Teachers disagree (43.8%), thus teachers

have not yet taken advantage of the skills they have in creating verb literacy (Dwi Shiera; Tatat Hartati, et al, 2022).

7. CONCLUSION

Overall, this qualitative study found that Edukit is very effective and beneficial for teachers and students of primary schools, special schools and inclusive primary schools. In addition to being a learning medium, Edukit can be developed as financial literacy, when teachers and students collaborate to create and sell the results of kriya literacy (craft literacy) to parents and the community. Another advantage of edukit is that bag materials are very cheap, easy to obtain, and you can use second-hand items (objects) that are not used. Thus Edukit is relevant to science literacy / environmental literacy and global issues.

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